

TRANSITION TO GREEN ECONOMY: PROBLEMS AND SOLUTIONS

Rustem Omirzakov

doctoral student at Karakalpak State University

omirzakov_r@karsu.uz

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11002803>

Abstract. *The transition to a green economy is a complex and challenging process that requires a fundamental shift in the way we produce, consume, and dispose of goods and services. While there are many benefits to transitioning to a green economy, including reduced environmental pollution, increased resource efficiency, and job creation, there are also a number of problems that need to be addressed. This article identifies some of the key problems associated with the transition to a green economy and proposes solutions to overcome these challenges.*

Keywords: *green economy, sustainability, environmental pollution, resource efficiency, job creation, economic growth, sustainable development.*

YASHIL IQTISODIYOTGA O‘TISH: MUAMMOLAR VA YECHIMLAR

Rustem Omirzakov

doktorant, Qoraqalpoq Davlat Universiteti

omirzakov_r@karsu.uz

Annotatsiya. *Yashil iqtisodiyotga o‘tish - bu mahsulot va xizmatlarni ishlab chiqarish, iste‘mol qilish va tasarruf etish usullarini tubdan o‘zgartirishni talab qiladigan murakkab va qiyin jarayon. Yashil iqtisodiyotga o‘tishning ko‘plab afzalliklari, jumladan, ifloslanish darajasini pasaytirish, resurslar samaradorligini oshirish va ish o‘rinlarini yaratish bo‘lsa-da, hal qilinishi kerak bo‘lgan qator muammolar ham mavjud. Ushbu maqola yashil iqtisodiyotga o‘tish bilan bog‘liq ba‘zi asosiy muammolarni aniqlaydi va ularni bartaraf etish uchun echimlarni taklif qiladi.*

Kalit so‘zlar: *yashil iqtisodiyot, barqarorlik, atrof-muhitning ifloslanishi, resurslar samaradorligi, ish o‘rinlarini yaratish, iqtisodiy o‘sish, barqaror rivojlanish.*

ПЕРЕХОД К "ЗЕЛеной" ЭКОНОМИКЕ: ПРОБЛЕМЫ И РЕШЕНИЯ

Рустем Умирзаков

докторант Каракалпакского государственного университета

omirzakov_r@karsu.uz

ORCID: 0009-0005-3317-5258

Аннотация. *Переход к "зеленой" экономике - сложный и трудный процесс, требующий фундаментальных изменений в том, как мы производим, потребляем и утилизируем товары и услуги. Хотя переход к "зеленой" экономике имеет множество преимуществ, включая снижение загрязнения окружающей среды, повышение эффективности использования ресурсов и создание новых рабочих мест, существует и ряд проблем, требующих решения. В данной статье определены некоторые ключевые*

проблемы, связанные с переходом к "зеленой" экономике, и предложены решения для их преодоления.

***Ключевые слова:** зеленая экономика, устойчивость, загрязнение окружающей среды, эффективность использования ресурсов, создание рабочих мест, экономический рост, устойчивое развитие.*

INTRODUCTION

Today we are witnessing unprecedented land degradation and loss of arable land 30 to 35 times faster than in the past. Drought and desertification are increasing annually, resulting in the loss of 12 million hectares of land and affecting poor communities around the world[1, 89]. As Joyce Msuya, Deputy Executive Director, UN-Environment, says: "Time is running short. ... It's clear that we need to transform the way our economies work, and the way we value the things that we consume." [2]

Since the industrial revolution, our economies have delivered huge advances in material prosperity. But this progress is increasingly imperilled by the very economic models which made it possible. Our economies are still measured and managed in ways that incentivise overconsumption, damage nature and social bonds, and drive climate change. In 2015 the global community committed to tackling these linked problems through the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) and the Paris Agreement on climate change. This can only be described as historic.[3]

The concept of the green economy

The concept of a green economy has been gaining traction in recent years as a way to address the challenges of environmental degradation and climate change. A green economy is one that is low-carbon, resource-efficient, and socially inclusive. It is an economy that promotes sustainable development and improves the well-being of all citizens.

The green economy is an economic framework that integrates considerations for the environment and sustainability into economic growth. It aims to generate economic development and job creation while ensuring that we don't deplete the planet's natural resources - which are essential for our survival. This approach focuses on reducing environmental risks and ecological scarcities. The UN defines the green economy as "low carbon, resource efficient and socially inclusive. In a green economy, growth in employment and income are driven by public and private investment into such economic activities, infrastructure and assets that allow reduced carbon emissions and pollution, enhanced energy and resource efficiency, and prevention of the loss of biodiversity and ecosystem services." [4] United Nations Environment Programme (UNEP) defined a green economy as "one that results in improved human well-being and social equity, while significantly reducing environmental risks and ecological scarcities. In its simplest expression, a green economy can be thought of as one, which is low carbon, resource efficient and socially inclusive. Other definitions have been proposed by various stakeholders, including some governments and coalition groups, but they generally describe the same core idea" (ECE/FAO, 2018)

"A green economy is a broad-ranging policy agenda and a tool to support the achievement of sustainable development, with an emphasis on aligning economic goals to social and environmental ones. The green economy agenda recognizes the potential of new sustainable technologies and green sectors to become the engine of a new development pathway". [5]

Methods

This article is based on a review of the literature on the transition to a green economy. The literature review included studies from a variety of disciplines, including economics, environmental science, and public policy. The studies were selected based on their relevance to the topic of the article and their quality.

The origin of the concept

The term green economy was first introduced by environmental economists in the 1989 report for the UK Government, 'Blueprint for a Green Economy'. This report, which focused on defining sustainable development and its implications for economic progress and policy, used the term green economy in its title but didn't delve into detail in the report itself. [6]

Following this, the authors expanded on the concept in two subsequent reports, 'Blueprint 2: Greening the World Economy' (1991) and 'Blueprint 3: Measuring Sustainable Development' (1994). These reports broadened the scope from environmental policy to incorporate global economic challenges like climate change and resource loss, building on decades of research in environmental economics. However, it wasn't until 2008 that the term gained global significance. With the backdrop of the global financial crisis, the United Nations Environment Programme (UNEP) promoted green stimulus packages, inspiring governments to incorporate green initiatives in their economic recovery plans. In October 2008, UNEP's Green Economy Initiative was launched, further cementing the concept's relevance [7]. As part of this initiative one of the original 'Blueprint' authors was asked to prepare a report outlining policies for economic recovery while enhancing global sustainability, this report is known as the 'Global Green New Deal' (2009). [8] The concept of the green economy gained further international attention in 2010 when the UNEP Global Ministerial Environment Forum recognized its potential to address global challenges. In the same year, the UN General Assembly designated the green economy as a central theme for the 2012 Rio+20 Conference, leading to significant discussions on the topic and renewed interest in this area of research. This renewed research interest resulted in the publication of UNEP's 2011 Green Economy Report, which provided a working definition of the green economy and was supported by various think tanks and commercial bodies. This period also saw numerous UN agencies, non-governmental organizations, and partnerships further exploring and promoting the green economy concept, establishing guiding principles, and assessing its benefits and risks. [9]

The green economy in Uzbekistan

The Government of Uzbekistan is committed to green growth and transformation towards a green economy. The Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated October 4, 2019, No. PD-4477, approved the strategy for the transition of the Republic of Uzbekistan to a green economy for the period 2019-2030. [10]

The main objectives of transition of the Republic of Uzbekistan to Green economy: (a) improving energy efficiency of the economy and rational consumption of natural resources through technological modernization and development of financial mechanisms; (b) inclusion in priority areas of public investment and spending of green criteria based on international best practices; (c) assistance in the implementation of pilot projects in the areas of transition to Green economy through the development of mechanisms of state incentives, public-private partnership and cooperation with international financial institutions; (d) development of a system of training

and retraining of personnel related to labor market in green economy; (e) taking measures to mitigate the negative impact of environmental disaster in the Aral Sea region; (f) strengthening international cooperation in the field of "green" economy, also through the conclusion of bilateral and multilateral agreement.[11]

RESULTS

Benefits of a Green Economy

Environmental Protection: A green economy reduces pollution, conserves natural resources, and mitigates climate change, ensuring a healthier planet for future generations.

Economic Growth: Green industries, such as renewable energy and energy efficiency, create new jobs and stimulate economic activity.

Social Equity: A green economy promotes social justice by addressing environmental disparities and providing opportunities for all.

Improved Health and Well-being: Reduced pollution and improved environmental quality lead to better health outcomes and increased well-being.

Key Elements of a Green Economy

Resource Efficiency: Reducing the use of energy, water, and materials through innovative technologies and practices.

Decarbonization: Transitioning to renewable energy sources and reducing carbon emissions from industries and transportation.

Sustainable Agriculture: Promoting sustainable farming practices that protect soil health, reduce water consumption, and minimize chemical inputs.

Green Infrastructure: Investing in parks, green spaces, and other natural infrastructure to improve air quality, reduce flooding, and enhance biodiversity.

Circular Economy: Adopting a circular economy model that emphasizes reuse, recycling, and waste reduction.

DISCUSSION

The transition to a green economy is not without its challenges.

Lack of investment in green technologies and infrastructure: The transition to a green economy requires significant investment in new technologies and infrastructure. This can be a challenge for governments and businesses, especially in developing countries.

Loss of jobs in traditional industries: The transition to a green economy may lead to job losses in traditional industries that are heavily reliant on fossil fuels and other unsustainable practices. This can have a negative impact on workers and their families.

Lack of consumer awareness about the benefits of green products and services: Consumers need to be aware of the benefits of green products and services in order to make informed choices. This can be a challenge, as green products and services are often more expensive than traditional products and services.

Lack of government support for green initiatives: Governments need to play a leadership role in the transition to a green economy. This includes providing financial support for green businesses, investing in green infrastructure, and creating policies that encourage sustainable practices.

Solutions

Increase investment in green technologies and infrastructure: Governments and businesses need to increase investment in green technologies and infrastructure. This can be done through a

variety of mechanisms, such as government subsidies, tax incentives, and public-private partnerships.

Provide support for workers who are displaced by the transition to a green economy: Governments and businesses need to provide support for workers who are displaced by the transition to a green economy. This can be done through job retraining programs, wage subsidies, and other forms of assistance.

Raise consumer awareness about the benefits of green products and services: Governments and businesses need to raise consumer awareness about the benefits of green products and services. This can be done through public education campaigns, media outreach, and other forms of communication.

Provide government support for green initiatives: Governments need to play a leadership role in the transition to a green economy. This includes providing financial support for green businesses, investing in green infrastructure, and creating policies that encourage sustainable practices.

CONCLUSION

Transitioning to a green economy is an essential step towards creating a sustainable and equitable future. By embracing resource efficiency, decarbonization, and social equity, we can unlock economic growth, protect our environment, and improve the well-being of our communities. Governments, businesses, and individuals must work together to overcome challenges and seize the opportunities presented by a green economy. The time for action is now, as we strive to build a more sustainable and prosperous world for generations to come. green economy is essential for the well-being of our planet and future generations. By embracing sustainable practices, investing in renewable energy, and promoting social equity, we can create a thriving and resilient economy that benefits all. Governments, businesses, and individuals must work together to make this transition a reality. A green economy is not just a choice; it is a necessity for a sustainable and prosperous future.

REFERENCES:

1. Omirzakov, R. (2023). SUSTAINABLE DEVELOPMENT GOALS AND ITS ROLE IN THE STATE POLICY OF THE REPUBLIC OF UZBEKISTAN IN THE FIELD OF ENVIRONMENTAL PROTECTION. International Journal Of Law And Criminology, 3(07), 89-93.
2. Msuya, Joyce (2019). We Are Past Pledging and Politicking: The Way forward in 2019 - A letter from Joyce Msuya, Acting Executive Director of UN Environment. <https://wedocs.unep.org/20.500.11822/27572>.
3. Principles, priorities & pathways for inclusive green economies // green economy coalition URL: <https://www.greeneconomycoalition.org/news-and-resources/principles-priorities-pathways-for-inclusive-green-economies> (дата обращения: 21.03.2023).
4. Green Economy: meaning and principles // greenly.earth URL: <https://greenly.earth/en-us/blog/company-guide/green-economy--meaning-and-principles>
5. Green economy // unece.org
6. Green economy // sustainabledevelopment.un.org URL: <https://sustainabledevelopment.un.org/index.php?menu>

- [=1446#:~:text=The%20term%20green%20economy%20was,Markandya%20and%20Barbier%2C%201989\).](#)
7. Green Economy: meaning and principles // www.unep.org URL: <https://www.unep.org/explore-topics/resource-efficiency/what-we-do/policy-and-strategy/green-economy#:~:text=The%20UN%20Environment%2Dled%20Green,in%20greening%20environmental%20unfriendly%20sectors>
 8. A Global Green New Deal // [sustainabledevelopment](http://sustainabledevelopment.un.org) URL: <https://sustainabledevelopment.un.org/index.php?page=view&type=400&nr=670&menu=1515#:~:text=The%20Global%20Green%20New%20Deal,for%20green%20stimulus%20programs%20as> (дата обращения: 21.03.2023).
 9. Towards a Green Economy: Pathways to Sustainable Development and Poverty Eradication // [sustainabledevelopment](http://sustainabledevelopment.un.org) URL: <https://sustainabledevelopment.un.org/index.php?Page=view&type=400&nr=126&menu=35> (дата обращения: 21.03.2023).
 10. Monitoring Uzbekistan's Progress towards Green Economy using the OECD Green Growth Indicators framework // search.oecd.org URL: <https://search.oecd.org/countries/uzbekistan/monitoringuzbekistansprogresstowardsgreenecomyusingtheoecdgreengrowthindicatorsframework.htm#:~:text=The%20Government%20of%20Uzbekistan%20is,for%20the%20period%202019%2D2030>.
 11. Strategy for the transition of the Republic of Uzbekistan to a Green economy in the period of 2019-2030. // FAOLEX Database URL: <https://www.fao.org/faolex/results/details/en/c/LEX-FAOC197240/#:~:text=The%20main%20objectives%20of%20transition,public%20investment%20and%20spending%20of>